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Factors affecting in-patient satisfaction in super specialty private hospitals - a case study of Burdwan district in West Bengal

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this article is to study the healthcare service providers' commitment to service quality and spot the factors which are responsible for customer satisfaction. The study has been conducted to find the patients'/ customers' awareness in regard to the quality of service provided by different super specialty private hospitals in Burdwan district.

Twelve independent variables have been considered to judge in-patients' satisfaction which are Punctuality, Sincerity, Employees' grooming, Customized service, Promptness in service, Motivation of the employees, Fair transaction Courteousness of the employees, Patient handling competency, Consistency in charges, State of the art facilities and Personal care. The results indicate that there is a strong association between customer satisfaction and a few of the above independent variables. The said variables would help healthcare organizations to make their patients gratified, which would subsequently result in the patients/customers being loyal to the hospital and thereby spread a positive word of mouth regarding the provider and its services.

Key words: Factor analysis, Patient satisfaction, Super specialty hospital

INTRODUCTION

India's healthcare sector is an upcoming and booming sector. Lifestyle changes among the majority of the Indian households has necessitated the need for quality healthcare in the country. The healthcare industry, as a service industry, needs to understand and meet the expectations of its customers i.e. the patients.

The service industry is a unique phenomenon in the national development of a country. Since the 1980s, the service industry has developed into an extremely important element in the development of many countries especially the developing and advanced countries (IBEF, 2013). Health Care Sector is one the important service sectors in India. India's economy is growing and the middle class has more disposable income to spend on healthcare services. The Government of India, too, is constantly developing all-inclusive policies on healthcare that aim to reinforce the sector. The sector holds great potential and promise and is looking forward to a healthy future (www.indianexpress.com).

However, with the increase in per capita income, the access to quality healthcare has increased for the majority of the population. Especially with the proliferation of medical insurance companies and the awareness of people regarding the health insurance, most families are nowadays covered under insurance. This has subsequently resulted in an increase in bed occupancy among hospitals, both public and private, as frequency of hospitalization, for treatment of certain diseases which require so and hitherto outside the reach of most people, have increased manifold. The Indian healthcare sector is estimated to reach US\$ 100 billion by 2015, growing 20 per cent year-on-year (y-o-y), as per rating agency Fitch. In India, 80% of the healthcare expenditure is borne by the patients and that borne by the state is 12%. The expenditure covered by insurance claims is 3%. As a result, the price sensitivity is quite high and the high-level healthcare facilities are not in the reach of patients (www.rncos.com/Report/IM054.htm).

The Government of Singapore Investment Corp and Goldman Sachs Group Inc are among the contributors that pumped 520 million US dollars into India's basic healthcare industry in 2012. This is a significant jump from the \$137 million invested in 2011. Analysts are expecting private equity investment in the sector to balloon to 1 billion dollars in 2013. Indian healthcare service providers are hoping that foreign investments will help upgrade technology and create employment opportunities. This will bring about potential benefits to the health sector and the economy at large (www.indianexpress.com).

India had around 80 per cent of hospital units and 80 per cent of hospital-beds in the public sector during 1974; post-liberalization in 1990s, the trend reversed and now has only 38 per cent in the public sector and has the most privatized health care system in the world (Ramchandran and Rajalakshmi, 2009). According to PricewaterhouseCoopers (2007), the private sector accounts for more than 80% of total healthcare spending in India.

In service marketing literature, service quality is generally defined as the overall assessment of a service by the customers, (Eshghi et al., 2008) or the extent to which a service meets customer's needs or expectations, (Asubonteng et al., 1996). Parasuraman et al., (1985) define service quality as "*The discrepancy between consumers' perceptions of services offered by a particular firm and their expectations about firms offering such services*". If what is perceived is below expectation, consumer judges quality as low and if what is perceived is meets or exceeds expectation then consumer sees quality to be high.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study, conducted in super specialty hospitals in Burdwan district, is to understand the satisfaction level of in-patients regarding various parameters.

This study aims to identify the most important factors affecting patient satisfaction in private hospitals in Burdwan district. It also helps to extend the understanding on the factors that may exist and its influence towards customer (patient) satisfaction, an important element in retaining a profitable business. The

justification behind selection of private hospitals over public hospitals is that in many studies the former have been found to be better service providers than the latter. The specific objective of the study includes

1. To identify the factors affecting customer satisfaction and subsequently naming them
2. To identify the variables that have significant association with customer satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The state of satisfaction depends on a number of both psychological and physical variables which correlate with satisfaction behaviors such as return and recommend rate. The level of satisfaction can also vary depending on other options the customer may have and other products against which the customer can compare the organization's products. A business ideally is continually seeking feedback to improve customer satisfaction. "Customer satisfaction provides a leading indicator of consumer purchase intentions and loyalty."Farris et al. (2010).

However, work done by Parasuraman et.al., between 1985 and 1988 provides the basis for the measurement of customer satisfaction with a service by using the gap between the customer's expectation of performance and their perceived experience of performance. This provides the measurer with a satisfaction "gap" which is objective and quantitative in nature.

Work done by Cronin and Taylor propose the "confirmation/disconfirmation" theory of combining the "gap" described by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry as two different measures (perception and expectation of performance) into a single measurement of performance according to expectation.

The 21st century is considered as the service industry century. Service industry is growing at a rapid pace across developed and developing countries. Services are deeds, processes and performances (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2008).

Broadly speaking, services include all economic activities whose output is not a physical product or construction is generally consumed at the time it is produced and provides added value in forms (convenience, amusement, timeliness, comfort or health) that are essentially intangible concerns of its first purchaser (Quinn, Baruch and Paquette, 1987).

Service has been entering every part of life from the most essential demands (such as eating, sleeping) to other entertainment needs (such as sport, traveling, cooking, and telecommunication). In other words, we readily define bank, hotel, restaurants, and beauty salon as being service-based business. Similarly said by Hung N. Bui (2004) service is an activity that impacts all parts of our life. Another definition of service is that a service is any activity or benefit that one party offers to another which is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything. Its product may or may not be tied to a physical product (Kotler, Armstrong, Saunders and Wong 1998). These modern marketers view services as a business that produces no tangible product.

It was stated in a study conducted by Gocek et al.(2007) that Customer satisfaction increase the existing customer loyalty, repurchase process, awareness of the people about the firm, decrease the price flexibility, the cost of gaining new customers.

Oliver (1980) found that customer satisfaction can be affected by expectation and disconfirmation. Expectation is seen as an adaptation level or a reference point used to compare actual performance with the perceived performance. The comparison resulted in disconfirmation. If perceived performances are higher than the reference point (expectation), it results in positive disconfirmation. If the perceived performances are lower than the expectation, it results in negative disconfirmation.

Ross et al. (1987) concluded that patient dissatisfaction is the result of an interaction

between expectations and perceived performance of service. If the patient has a positive expectation and it is substantially disconfirmed by perception of poor service performance, then the patient will be dissatisfied. The opposite is also true.

Yesilada and Direktor (2010) extracted the dimensions of the SERVQUAL model in both public and private hospitals. Private hospitals appeared with smaller gaps between expectations and perceptions (not negligibly small), as compared to the public hospitals and were perceived as better service providers.

In service industries, customer satisfaction is always influenced by the quality of interactions between the customers and the personnel involved in the contact services (Kotler, 2010). In India there is presence of both private and public sector healthcare providers. The private health care system in India though has grown vastly over the years and is well established and flourishing. At the time of Independence, the private health sector accounted for only 5 to 10 per cent of total patient care. In 2004, the share of private sector in total hospitalized treatment was estimated at 58.3 per cent in rural areas and 61.8 per cent in urban areas (Rao, 2012).

Parasuraman et al., (1985), developed a model of service quality after carrying out a study on four service settings: retail banking, credit card services, repair and maintenance of electrical appliances, and long-distance telephone services. The SERVQUAL model represents service quality as the discrepancy between a customer's expectations of service offering and the customer's perceptions of the service received. What this model strives to measure exactly is the consumer perception of the service quality which depends on the size of the gap between expected service and perceived service which in turn, depends on the gaps under the control of the service provider such as delivery of service, marketing. This measurement of service quality is based on both on how consumer evaluates the service delivery process and the outcome of the service. A good service quality is considered as one which meets or exceeds consumer's expectation of the service.

The SERVQUAL model was made of ten dimensions of service quality when created; tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, communication, credibility, security, competence, courtesy, understanding the customer, and access but later on these dimensions were reduced to five because some dimensions were overlapping. Now it includes Tangibles- physical facilities, equipments, and staff appearance. Reliability- ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately; Responsiveness- willingness to help customers and provide prompt service; Assurance- knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence and Empathy- caring, individual attention the firm provides its customers. (Parasuraman et al., 1988, p.23).

Hospitals in the developed world recognize the importance of delivering patient satisfaction as a strategic variable and a crucial determinant of long-term viability and success (Makoul et al. 1995; Davies and Ware 1988). McAlexander et al., (1993) observed that the private health care sector has begun practicing consumer oriented strategies to genuinely meet the needs of consumers in developing countries

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The sample comprised of in-patients from four super specialty hospitals in Burdwan district of West Bengal. The respondents were the patients admitted to those hospitals / relatives of the patients attending in those hospitals. In this descriptive research, data were collected from 120 respondents with the help of a structured questionnaire.

Twelve independent variables have been considered to judge in-patients' satisfaction for this study, **which are Punctuality (Variable 1) , Sincerity (Variable 2), Employees' grooming (Variable 3), Customized service (Variable 4), Promptness in service (Variable 5), Motivation of the employees (Variable 6), Fair transaction (Variable 7), Courteousness of the employees (Variable 8), Patient handling competency (Variable 9), Consistency in charges (Variable 10), State of the art facilities (Variable11) and Personal care (Variable 12).**

A statistical tool namely “Factor analysis” has been used for judging the association between dependent and independent variables and also to ascertain which of the independent variable/s by virtue of being closely associated may be grouped into one factor.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A normality test was conducted to decide on the statistical analysis method for use. Results of statistical analyses using the *Kolmogorov Smirnov Test* indicated a value of $p > 0.05$ for all the variables of sample data. This means that the samples are normally distributed. Then the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett's Test was conducted, the results of which are shown in *Table – 1* below:

TABLE – 1

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.818
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	777.624
	df	66
	Sig.	.000

Based on KMO measure of sampling adequacy test in *Table – 1* of this study, it was found that the factor analysis data was appropriate with the value of 0.818, which falls between the range of being great and appropriate for factor analysis. Bartlett's Test was utilized with the result indicating a highly significant value with $p=0.000$ ($p<0.001$) and therefore factor analysis was appropriate.

The number of factors extracted can also be determined in a way so that the cumulative percentage of variance extracted by the variables reaches a satisfactory level. *Table – 2* below shows the total variance explained.

TABLE – 2									
Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% Variance	of Cumulative %	Total	% Variance	of Cumulative %	Total	% Variance	of Cumulative %
1	5.524	46.034	46.034	5.524	46.034	46.034	4.044	33.696	33.696
2	1.420	11.835	57.869	1.420	11.835	57.869	2.371	19.761	53.457
3	1.183	9.858	67.728	1.183	9.858	67.728	1.713	14.271	67.728
4	.939	7.825	75.553						
5	.666	5.550	81.103						
6	.571	4.758	85.861						
7	.488	4.063	89.924						
8	.355	2.956	92.881						
9	.258	2.153	95.034						
10	.240	2.000	97.034						
11	.204	1.703	98.737						
12	.152	1.263	100.000						

In the above table, the cumulative percentage of variance extracted by three factors is 67.728% which is quite satisfactory. Then the rotated component matrix is conducted with the above variables. The results are displayed below in *Table – 3*:

TABLE - 3

Rotated Component Matrix^a			
	Component		
	1	2	3
Var 6	.807		
Var 5	.790		
Var 3	.761		
Var 4	.758		
Var 8	.651		
Var 9	.630		
Var 12	.543		
Var 10		.832	
Var 7		.742	
Var 11		.647	
Var 1			.882
Var 2			.734
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations.			

However, from the results obtained in the *Rotated Component Matrix in Table – 3* above, all the twelve variables can be accepted for further analysis. These variables were then subjected to reshuffle and reduction. This reshuffle and reduction is possible because the variables are related. The rating given to any one variable is partially the result of the influence of other variables.

In the rotated component matrix table, broadly three factors have been identified consisting of twelve variables. These are:

Factor - 1 consisting of variables like “**Motivation of the employees, Promptness in service, Employees’ grooming, Customized service, Courteousness of the employees, Patient handling competency and Personal care**” is loaded as 0.807, 0.790, 0.761, 0.758, 0.651, 0.630 and 0.543 respectively.

Similarly, Factor - 2 consisting of variables like “**Consistency in charges, Fair transaction and State of the art facilities**” is loaded as 0.832, 0.742 and 0.647 respectively.

Factor - 3 consisting of variables like “**Punctuality and Sincerity**” is loaded as 0.882 and 0.734 respectively.

In the rotated component matrix Factor 1 has high coefficients for variables **Motivation of the employees, Promptness in service, Employees’ grooming, Customized service , Courteousness of the employees, Patient handling competency and Personal care**; Factor 2 has high coefficients for variables “**Consistency in charges, Fair transaction and State of the art facilities**” and Factor 3 has high coefficients for variables “**Punctuality and Sincerity**” and therefore the said variables are aggregated in their respective factors.

The naming of the Factors are then carried out which is elaborated in *Table – 4*.

TABLE - 4**NAMING OF THE FACTORS**

FACTOR 1

MOTIVATION OF THE EMPLOYEES	STAFF EMPATHY AND RESPONSIVENESS
PROMPTNESS IN SERVICE	
EMPLOYEES' GROOMING	
CUSTOMIZED SERVICE	
COURTEOUSNESS OF THE EMPLOYEES	
PATIENT HANDLING COMPETENCY	
PERSONAL CARE	

FACTOR 2

CONSISTENCY IN CHARGES	FAIR AND PROPORTIONATE DEALINGS
FAIR TRANSACTION	
STATE OF THE ART FACILITIES	

FACTOR 3

PUNCTUALITY	STAFF RELIABILITY
SINCERITY	

In the above table, Factor 1 is labeled as “**STAFF EMPATHY AND RESPONSIVENESS**”, Factor 2 is labeled as “**COMMENSURATE AND FAIR DEALINGS**” and Factor 3 is labeled as “**STAFF RELIABILITY**”.

Finally after factor analysis, the results are required to be validated. For the same, an important statistical tool like regression analysis has been used showing R – square values.

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is performed with dependent variable as **Staff Empathy and Responsiveness (Factor 1)** and independent variables as **Employees’ grooming (Var 3), Customized service (Var 4), Promptness in service (Var 5), Motivation of the employees (Var 6), Courteousness of the employees (Var 8), Patient handling competency (Var 9) and Personal care (Var 12)** to see the fitness of the model (**Refer Table No.5A**). Another table i.e. **Table-5B shows R-Square value** of 0.886 and **adjusted R-Square value** of 0.879 which are reasonably fit for the analysis. A Durbin-Watson of 2.2 indicates that the error terms are relatively free of autocorrelation. The **ANOVA Table (Table No.5C)** shows an F value of 124.434 and strong significance level of 0.000 (p<0.01). Thus it is clear that the means of the above seven predictor variables are not all equal to each other and therefore they can be used to predict the dependent variable **Staff Empathy and Responsiveness (Factor 1)**. Further from the next table (**Table No.5D**), the results show that apart from Var 5, Var 9 and Var 12 rest of the variables are significant (p<0.01) with Beta (0.204, 0.333, 0.254 and 0.253) and corresponding t-values (4.369, 6.664, 4.471 and 5.607).

TABLE 5A

Variables Entered/Removed^b

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Var 12, Var 8, Var 4, Var 9, Var 3, Var 5, Var 6 ^a	.	Enter

a. All requested variables entered.

b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1

TABLE 5B

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.941 ^a	.886	.879	.34792758	2.202
a. Predictors: (Constant), Var 12, Var 8, Var 4, Var 9, Var 3, Var 5, Var 6					
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1					

TABLE 5C

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	105.442	7	15.063	124.434	.000 ^a
	Residual	13.558	112	.121		
	Total	119.000	119			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Var 12, Var 8, Var 4, Var 9, Var 3, Var 5, Var 6						
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1						

TABLE 5D

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-5.461	.210		-26.004	.000
	Var 3	.256	.059	.204	4.369	.000
	Var 4	.351	.053	.333	6.664	.000
	Var 5	.120	.060	.112	2.019	.046
	Var 6	.251	.056	.254	4.471	.000
	Var 8	.309	.055	.253	5.607	.000
	Var 9	.026	.049	.026	.536	.593
	Var 12	.006	.042	.006	.154	.878
a. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1						

The results indicate that 4 out of 7 of the independent variables have significant influence on **Factor 1 (Staff Empathy and Responsiveness)**. By examining the t statistic for all the independent variables it is apparently confirmed that **Employees' grooming (Variable 3), Customized service (Variable 4), Motivation of the employees (Variable 6) and Courteousness of the employees (Variable 8)** have significant relationship with customer satisfaction due to strong significance level ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, Variable 5 i.e. **Promptness in service** is also significant at 5% level ($p < 0.05$). It is to be noted that Variable 9 and variable 12 i.e. **Patient handling competency and Personal care** respectively do not have impact on customer satisfaction as they are not significant even at 5% level ($p < 0.05$). Therefore it may be inferred that employees who are well groomed, motivated and courteous are able to give better customized service which in turn leads to staff empathy and increased responsiveness to the concerns of the patients.

Regression analysis is also performed with dependent variable as **Fair and Proportionate Dealings (Factor 2)** and independent variables as **Fair transaction (Var 7), Consistency in charges (Var 10) and State of the art facilities (Var 11)** to see the fitness of the model (Refer Table No.6A). Another table i.e. **Table - 6B shows R-Square value** of 0.879 and **adjusted R-Square value** of 0.875 which are

also reasonably fit for the analysis. A Durbin-Watson of 1.99 indicates that the error terms are relatively free of autocorrelation. The **ANOVA Table (Table No.6C)** shows an F value of 279.837 and strong significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). Thus it is clear that the means of the above three predictor variables are not all equal to each other and therefore it can be used to predict the dependent variable **Fair and Proportionate Dealings (Factor 2)**. Further from the next table (**Table No. 6D**), the results show that all the variables are significant ($p < 0.01$) with Beta (0.420, 0.564 and 0.151) and corresponding t values (11.097, 14.234 and 3.759).

TABLE 6A

Variables Entered/Removed ^b			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Var 11, Var 7, Var 10 ^a	.	Enter
a. All requested variables entered.			
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1			

TABLE 6B

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.937 ^a	.879	.875	.35290302	1.999
a. Predictors: (Constant), Var 11, Var 7, Var 10					
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1					

TABLE 6C

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	104.553	3	34.851	279.837	.000 ^a
	Residual	14.447	116	.125		
	Total	119.000	119			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Var 11, Var 7, Var 10						
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1						

TABLE 6D

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-5.388	.208		-25.944	.000
	Var 7	.592	.053	.420	11.097	.000
	Var 10	.557	.039	.564	14.234	.000
	Var 11	.164	.044	.151	3.759	.000
a. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 2 for analysis 1						

The results indicate that all three independent variables have significant influence on **Factor 2 (Fair and Proportionate Dealings)**. By examining the t statistic for all three independent variables it is apparently confirmed that **Fair transaction (Var 7), Consistency in charges (Var 10) and State of the art facilities (Var 11)** have significant relationship with customer satisfaction due to strong significance level ($p < 0.01$). Therefore it may be inferred that the hospitals whose charges are reasonable and commensurate with the facilities provided by them, have fair and proportionate dealings with the customers.

Regression analysis is again performed with dependent variable as **Staff Reliability (Factor 3)** and independent variables as **Punctuality (Var 1) and Sincerity (Var 2)** to see the fitness of the model (Refer **Table No. 7A**). Another table i.e. **Table - 7B shows R-Square value** of 0.872 and **adjusted R-Square value** of 0.870 which are also reasonably fit for the analysis. A Durbin-Watson of 1.7 indicates that the error terms are relatively free of autocorrelation. The **ANOVA Table (Table No. 7C)** shows an F value of 399.202 and strong significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). Thus it is clear that the means of the above two predictor variables are not all equal to each other and therefore it can be used to predict the dependent variable **Staff Reliability (Factor 3)**. Further from the next table (**Table No. 7D**), the results show that all the variables are significant ($p < 0.01$) with Beta (0.686 and 0.363) and corresponding t values (17.467 and 9.249).

TABLE 7A
Variables Entered/Removed^b

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Var 2, Var 1 ^a	.	Enter
a. All requested variables entered.			
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 3 for analysis 1			

TABLE 7B
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.934 ^a	.872	.870	.36055134	1.700
a. Predictors: (Constant), Var 2, Var 1					
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 3 for analysis 1					

TABLE 7C
ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	103.790	2	51.895	399.202	.000 ^a
	Residual	15.210	117	.130		
	Total	119.000	119			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Var 2, Var 1						
b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 3 for analysis 1						

TABLE 7D

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-4.179	.172		-24.228	.000
	Var 1	.578	.033	.686	17.467	.000
	Var 2	.446	.048	.363	9.249	.000
a. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 3 for analysis 1						

The results indicate that those two independent variables have significant influence on **Factor 3 (Staff Reliability)**. By examining the t statistic for all the independent variables it is apparently confirmed that **Punctuality (Var 1) and Sincerity (Var 2)** have significant relationship due to strong significance level ($p < 0.01$) with customer satisfaction. Therefore it may be inferred that since the employees are punctual and sincere in serving the patients, it generates a feel good factor among the patients and their relatives and they look towards the hospital staff as a unit who could be relied upon.

Thus to summarize the results we may state that Punctuality (Var 1), Sincerity (Var 2), Employees' grooming (Var 3), Customized service (Var 4), Motivation of the employees (Var 6), Fair transaction (Var 7), Courteousness of the employees (Var 8), Consistency in charges (Var 10) and State of the art facilities (Var 11) have a significant impact on overall customer satisfaction.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

From the statistical result, it is found that **"Staff Empathy and Responsiveness"** consisting of variables like Employees' grooming, Customized service, Motivation of the employees, and Courteousness of the employees (since Promptness in service, Patient handling competency and Personal care were not found significant), **"Fair and Proportionate Dealings"** consisting of variables like Consistency in charges, Fair transaction and State of the art facilities and **"Staff Reliability"** consisting of variables like Punctuality and Sincerity are significantly related to patient satisfaction. These three factors are imperative in providing an adequate service which will be able to make the patient / customer happy and pleased. According to the model of customers' satisfaction by Zeithaml and Bitner (1996), "quality service is the focus of assessments reflecting the patients' / customers' perception on satisfaction". It may be acknowledged that delivering quality service is only possible when a health care service provider focuses on the above stated areas viz. Employees' grooming, Customized service, Motivation of the employees, Courteousness of the employees, Consistency in charges, Fair transaction, State of the art facilities, Punctuality and Sincerity. So our findings fall in line with what Zeithaml and Bitner (1996) proposed.

Thus in this study **"Staff Empathy and Responsiveness"**, **"Fair and Proportionate Dealings"** and **"Staff Reliability"** are the three exclusive areas for delivering quality service which in turn will satisfy the customers in health care sector.

Further Grönroos (1996) identified in a study that "satisfaction is a phenomenon where the performance and benefits of the products exceed the expectations of the customers. Customer satisfaction increases the existing customer loyalty, awareness of the people about the firm, decrease the price flexibility, the cost of gaining new customers and prevent the customer being affected from competitive enterprise". What Grönroos (1996) stated is only possible when a service provider can identify the factors in a service product which will have a link with customers' expectations. Our views are in line with the views of

Grönroos (1996) as we have identified those factors and also established relationship with customer/patient satisfaction.

Therefore the recognition of the above factors and their relationship with customer/ patient satisfaction will give an impetus to the growth of the specific sector.

To the service providers, the three factors comprising of the above stated variables are of supreme importance to make an ever ending lucrative relationship with the existing customers and to haul new customers as well. A strong dependable relationship can be created that will give the service provider / company an aggressive edge for future survival.

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